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HPV E4 protein binds keratins KRT18 and KRT8.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We employed a proteomics approach for systematic discovery of HPV E4 interacting proteins. We demonstrate here that HPV E4 protein binds keratins KRT18 and KRT8. The proteomic data support a role for HPV E4 in late stages of the viral life cycle in differentiated, keratinized layers of the skin.

Citations

1. Doorbar, J., Ely, S., Sterling, J., McLean, C. and Crawford, L., 1991. Specific interaction between HPV-16 E1–E4 and cytokeratins results in collapse of the epithelial cell intermediate filament network. *Nature*, 352(6338), pp.824-827.